

EXPLORERS

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NJIT

New Jersey Institute
of Technology

New Jersey Institute of Technology

Department of Electrical and Computer
Engineering

Advanced Networking Laboratory

ece.njit.edu

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New Jersey Institute of Technology is ranked #1 nationally by Forbes for the upward economic mobility of its lowest-income students and is among the top 2% of public colleges and universities in return on educational investment.

NJIT is one of only three R1 research universities in New Jersey. The **Advanced Networking Laboratory** (ANL) at NJIT engages in research to improve the performance, dependability, and trustworthiness of telecommunications networks. ANL's goals are to identify, model, simulate, and demonstrate next-generation networking technologies, and to add to the knowledge base for next generation networks; to train tomorrow's network engineering innovators; and to foster industrial collaboration and international partnerships. ANL innovations are disseminated via patent disclosures, journal publications, conference presentations, and presentations to funding sponsors and prospective users. Current research focuses on green communications and networking, cloud/fog/edge computing, drone-assisted networking, and localization.

READY FOR:

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

OPEN IDEAS

FUNDED BY

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OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

n/a

